

Quantum Mechanics and the Relationship Between $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ And Classical Physics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 21, 2026

Newtonian mechanics presents a simultaneous description of dynamics $x(t)$ and interactions ($F=dp/dt$) because it assumes infinite resolution, i.e. $dx \rightarrow 0$, $dt \rightarrow 0$. We have argued in a previous note (1), that quantum mechanics follows from free particle quantum mechanics, which in turn follows from special relativity. Special relativity uses the notion of $x=vt$ and provides formulas for $E=mc^2/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and $p=mv/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ even with no free particle quantum mechanical notions. We have also argued in previous notes, however, that these classical concepts are present in the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ which we have argued (2) acts as a kind of free particle potential. This potential, however, has the same value for x , t and $x+\hbar/p$, $t+\hbar/E$ and so we have suggested that free particle quantum mechanics is comprised of two parts. The first is a complex probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which describes possible interactions with a free particle and the second is $x=vt$. In other words, interactions and dynamics are split, but the interaction probability depends on classical notions such as $x=vt$, p and E . In the limit of \hbar/p and $\hbar/E \ll 1$, the interaction resolution becomes the Newtonian $dx \rightarrow 0$, $dt \rightarrow 0$. Thus, as in (1), we argue that quantum and classical mechanics are intertwined.

In (3), entitled Unifying Quantum and Classical Dynamics, a similar argument for the intertwining of quantum mechanics and classical mechanics is presented, but in a different manner. The basic argument of (3) seems to be that quantum mechanics, written in the Heisenberg approach, yields operator equations which are identical in form to classical equations, in particular, $d/dt X(t) = P(t)$ and $d/dt d/dt X(t) = -d/dx V(X(t))$. Here $X(t)$ and $P(t)$ are operators given by $X(t) = \exp(iH t) X(0) \exp(-iHt)$ (and a similar expression for $P(t)$). We try to show that given that free particle quantum mechanics is directly linked to special relativity and hence to the acceptance of $x=vt$, that in the free particle case, any operator description of $d/dt X(t) = P(t)$ cannot yield any result other than a classical one because no interaction is occurring. In other words, quantum mechanics is directly linked to classical mechanics at the free particle level. Later, one takes a superposition (OR probability addition) of $\exp(ipx)$ s, as in the case of bound states. In such a case, one deals with average interactions and so one must be careful when interpreting $d/dt d/dt X(t) = -d/dx V(X(t))$ as the system description is now an average one.

Quantum Free Particle Mechanics, Special Relativity and Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics simultaneously describes dynamics ($x(t)$) with interactions $F=dp/dt$ using infinite resolution $dx \rightarrow 0$, $dt \rightarrow 0$. If a particle does not interact, however, i.e. is a free particle, then there is only dynamics, i.e.

$$x=vt \quad ((1))$$

v is formally defined as dx/dt , but for a free particle and initial $x=0$, $t=0$, ((1)) holds as a basic definition of the concept of velocity and this does not change for a free quantum particle as long as it does not interact. ((1)) is an essential equation for developing special relativity because this theory deals with viewing a particle (say with rest mass) in one frame and comparing what one

sees in this frame to what one sees in a frame moving with say a constant velocity $-v$. Thus, the concept of a constant v must exist and is given by ((1)). In fact, it is ((1)) which ensures that x' and t' cannot be the same as $x=0, t$ for a rest mass m_0 at rest. In a moving frame $-v$, m_0 is seen to move at v and if $x'=0, t'=0$ are the initial points, $x'/t'=v$ and so these must be different from $x=0, t$ which does not have this ratio. From special relativity, one obtains the values for free energy and momentum:

$$E = \frac{m_0 c^2}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} \quad p = \frac{m_0 v}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} \quad ((2))$$

We have argued in previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics follows from special relativity and so in that case, the notions of E, p and $x=vt$ must be accepted as existing equations. Even if one does not believe that free particle follows from special relativity, the free particle wavefunction (which we call a complex probability)

$$\exp(-iEt + ipx) \quad ((3))$$

makes use of E and p and these must be defined. They are via special relativity, but this requires a definition of v , namely $x=vt$. Thus, even in quantum mechanics (for a free particle) it is not enough to use ((3)), one must explicitly present $x=vt$ and definitions for p and E . $x=vt$, however, are the dynamical description of the particle and it is entirely classical. How can this apply to quantum mechanics? We argue that it applies as long as an interaction does not occur. ((3)), on the other hand, describes an interaction. It shows that there is an uncertainty in x of \hbar/p and so a free particle may interact probabilistically with one slit or the other in a 2-slit apparatus if the slit separation is about \hbar/p . Furthermore, an interaction occurs when a particle is created, or possibly interacts with a vector magnetic field and so $\exp(ipx)$ may have a phase shift $\exp(ipx + i \text{ phase shift})$. This, however, manifests itself in an interaction, not while the particle is moving according to $x=vt$. One might argue that the infinite resolution of x, t in $x=vt$ cannot hold as there are uncertainties of $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$, but again that comes into play when one has interaction.

We belabour the point of $x=vt$ because we argue that free particle quantum mechanics must include this classical equation. We further argue that more complicated (e.g. bound state quantum mechanics) follows from an OR addition of $\exp(ipx)$ s and classical conservation of energy. The stress that in any quantum formalism (e.g. the Heisenberg operator representation of quantum mechanics), in the free particle scenario, must be consistent with $x=vt$. We suggest this is why classical and quantum mechanics are intertwined in many ways, although quantum mechanics allows for probabilistic interaction via ((3)), spin, entanglement and other nonclassical features.

The Case of $d/dt X(t) = P(t)$

In (3), it is argued that quantum and classical mechanics are intertwined because the Heisenberg operator representation of quantum mechanics yields the two equations:

$$d/dt X(t) = P(t) \quad ((4))$$

$$d/dt d/dt X(t) = - d/dx V(X(t)) \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{Here } X(t) = \exp(i H t) X(0) \exp(-iHt) \text{ and } P(t) = \exp(iHt) P(0) \exp(-iHt) \quad ((6))$$

H is the Hamiltonian operator $-1/2m d/dx d/dx$ for a free particle ((7)).

As a result, one may consider the LHS and RHS of ((4)) to see if they are equivalent.

$$\text{RHS } P(t) = \exp(i (-1/2m t d/dx d/dx)) (-id/dx) \exp(-1/2m t d/dx d/dx) \quad ((8))$$

H and p commute and so the RHS is $-id/dx$ which acting on $\exp(ipx)$ yields p. p is a classical number which is a function of v, which in turn must be understood in terms of $x=vt$.

$$\begin{aligned} & d/dt \{ \exp(-i1/2m t d/dx d/dx) X(0) \exp(i 1/2m t d/dx d/dx) \} \\ &= -i/2m d/dx d/dx \exp(iHt) X(0) \exp(-iHt) + \exp(iHt) X(0) \exp(-iHt) i/2m d/dx d/dx \end{aligned}$$

The first term is: $-i/2m 2 d/dx + \exp(iHt) X(0) \exp(-Ht) (-2/m d/dx d/x)$ so

$$d/dt X(t) = P(t) \text{ or } -id/dx \quad ((9))$$

In (3), it is argued that classical mechanics appears in quantum mechanics because of ((9)). We argue, however, that if a quantum formalism is used for a free particle, it cannot violate $x=vt$, but must rather verify it. A free particle has no interactions and so all that is left are dynamics which are described entirely by $x=vt$. Even given $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, this idea cannot be changed and so it is not a revelation that ((9)) holds, it must hold, otherwise the notion of $x=vt$ would not exist and there would then be no definition for E and p in $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

We argue that a free particle quantum state is a key concept because as a probability, one may write an OR situation for a more complicated situation (e.g. bound state)

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((10))$$

More complicated quantum mechanics (ignoring spin, antiparticles, entanglement etc) follows from averaging the free particle. As a result, we do not focus on equation ((5)) from (3) because even though it is of the form of Newton's second law, averages are involved. Nevertheless, classical physics is still present in a single particle quantum bound state at any energy level because the Schrodinger equation is a classical conservation of energy equation, albeit using averages:

$$\{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \} + V(x) = E \quad ((11))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have argued in (1) that quantum mechanics and classical mechanics are intertwined in the quantum regime. Even in the case of a free particle, i.e. one that does not interact, $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, the quantum probability linked with interactions applies together with $x=vt$. The classical result $x=vt$ must be considered a priori, we argue, because it is used to define p and E . As a result, the dynamics of a free particle are given by $x=vt$. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is linked with interactions as in 2-slit interference etc.

In (3), it is also argued that quantum mechanics and classical ideas are intertwined, but to prove this, the authors write the equations $d/dx X(t) = P(t)$ and $d/dt d/dt X(t) = -d/dx V(X(t))$ in the Heisenberg operator formalism. We argue that for the first equation and the case of a free particle one must obtain $x=vt$ and so it is really the notion of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ together with $x=vt$ which shows the intertwining of classical and quantum mechanics, as bound states etc are formed from superpositions of $\exp(ipx)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Both Quantum Mechanics and Newtonian Mechanics As Approximations? (preprint, zenodo, 2026)
- 2,. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Mechanics and Writing the LHS of $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ in terms of a Gradient? (preprint, zenodo, 2026)
3. Shaikh, A. and Qureshi, T. Unifying Quantum and Classical Dynamics (2026)
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/reader/15c85731362ce627b57167e0c6c62825ba07983>